

BRIDGE Mentorship Initiative

Transforming Epidemiological Research Practices by fostering research integrity and research fairness (version 1.2)

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Preface

The BRIDGE mentorship initiative is based on the BRIDGE guidelines for good practice in epidemiology. It has been initiated by epidemiologists and public health professionals based at KIT Royal Tropical Institute (Netherlands) and Institute of Tropical Medicine (Belgium) but is envisaged as an initiative that brings together and is ultimately owned by epidemiologists around the globe.

The initiative is intended as a long-term non-funded programme which leverages on professional intrinsic motivation to contribute to the committees and activities. Funding may be sought for pre-specified activities (e.g. meetings or other network opportunities).

This blueprint is intended as a source document. It describes the mentorship initiative in detail, including all anticipated procedures and roles and responsibilities of different individuals and committees. The primary target audience consists of: 1) mentors; 2) mentees; 3) steering committee members; 4) organising committee members.

This blueprint will be updated on a regular basis to ensure that it describes the current procedures, roles and responsibilities. Dates of revisions and major changes from previous versions are summarised in the table below.

Version	Date	Change from previous version
1.1	June 2023	First version for circulation
1.2	March 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- The name was changed to “BRIDGE mentorship initiative” because the previous name already existed.- The terminology was revised. Rather than trying to distinguish <i>coaches</i> from <i>mentors</i>, we now try to describe a “BRIDGE mentoring style” by referring to relevant elements from the concepts of coaching, mentoring, and reverse mentoring. Reverse mentoring is now less prominent.- The logo was updated and spelling mistakes and inconsistencies were corrected.- Timelines and annexes for the round 1 pilot have been updated.

Executive summary

Recent developments in research integrity led by Global South researchers have placed research fairness and equity at the centre of a renewed understanding of research integrity. Mentoring is often proposed as a strategy to enhance research integrity and reduce misconduct. While mentoring is traditionally seen as an exchange of knowledge and skills from more senior to more junior professionals, “reverse mentoring” could also be relevant for research integrity. The BRIDGE guidelines for good epidemiological practice can be a useful tool to support a mentoring process for global health epidemiologists by framing conversations on integrity and fairness throughout a study’s life cycle. Based on these considerations, this blueprint outlines the development and piloting of a mentoring programme for global health epidemiologists based on the BRIDGE guidelines.

The aim of the BRIDGE mentorship initiative is to promote research integrity and fairness in global health epidemiological studies. The specific objectives are:

1. To equip epidemiologists with skills to act as mentors on research integrity and fairness
2. To offer mentorship opportunities to researchers embarking on an epidemiological study
3. To create a support network of researchers committed to research fairness and integrity and to promote exchanges of best practices to deal with dilemmas related to research integrity and fairness in global health epidemiology
4. To create platforms to promote life-long learning and constructive dialogue as a means to create working cultures conducive for research integrity and fairness

The core of the BRIDGE mentorship initiative is the creation of one-on-one matches between mentors and mentees and the facilitation of structured exchanges between them throughout a one-year implementation of an epidemiological study. We envisage the initiative to be implemented as a series of mentoring rounds organised by different organising committees with overall guidance and oversight by the BRIDGE steering committee. After mentors and mentees have completed a one-year mentoring round, they will be invited to join the BRIDGE community of practice (CoP), an online platform that facilitates long-term collaborative learning and knowledge sharing.

1. Introduction

1.1 Rationale

Recent developments in research integrity led by Global South researchers have placed research fairness and equity at the centre of a renewed understanding of research integrity. This case is compellingly made by the Cape Town Statement on fairness, equity and diversity in research resulting from the 7th World Conference on Research Integrity [1]. While the research integrity agenda has traditionally concentrated on issues such as research misconduct and the importance of reproducibility, the Cape Town Statement “added the myriad ways in which research programmes and practices disadvantage those living in low and middle-income countries (LMICs) to the suite of issues that threaten the integrity of science”. This understanding of research integrity is crucial for global health, as a discipline which is often conducted in partnership involving researchers and organisations in both high income countries (HICs) and LMICs. This not only broadens the range of professional standards and values that global health researchers need to consider on a daily basis, but also adds complex layers related to unconscious biases and power relations rooted in colonial legacies.

Mentoring is often proposed as a strategy to enhance research integrity and reduce misconduct [2-4]. Mentoring is a personal development approach based on the use of one-to-one conversations to enhance an individual's skills, knowledge or work performance. As Bird argued, mentors are critically important to career development and professional success as they are “willing and able to share their experience and expertise, [...] to reflect on their successes and failures, and can explain what they have learned”. Furthermore, as Bird further argues, while technical skills can be obtained through books and courses, mentors play a key role in the transfer of professional skills specific to research (how to write and review manuscripts, how to manage a laboratory, how to obtain funding). In addition, mentors also play a unique role in helping young(er) professionals understand professional standards, conventions and ethical values (which committees to join, how to engage with collaborators, responsibilities of authorship). As such, mentors act as role models for mentees, with important implications for research integrity: exemplary role modelling can foster safe professional environments conducive to good research practices, while dubious role modelling can lead to the exact opposite.

While mentoring is traditionally seen as an exchange of knowledge and skills from more senior to more junior professionals, “reverse mentoring” could also be relevant for research integrity.

Indeed, Pizzolato and Dierickx have argued that senior academics are not always best placed to transfer research integrity competencies to their junior counterparts and proposed the concept of

“reverse mentoring” [5]¹. This practice pairs a younger employee acting as the mentor to share expertise with an older colleague as the mentee. Reverse mentoring was formally pioneered at General Electric in 1999 to facilitate the transfer of new emerging technologies and IT skills but also showed added benefits in terms of “building cross-generational relationships, creating equity and equality within the working environment, creating a two-way flow of new competencies, awareness, skills and establishing a better understanding of the organisational environment” [5].

The BRIDGE guidelines for good epidemiological practice can be a useful tool to support a mentoring process for global health epidemiologists by framing conversations on integrity and fairness throughout a study’s life cycle. The BRIDGE guidelines were developed specifically to bring together research integrity and research fairness principles in one practical checklist to guide researchers along a research project [6]. The six standards and accompanying criteria cover all steps in the implementation of a study, from study preparation to dissemination of results (Figure 1) and help ensure research is conducted according to research integrity and fairness principles.

Figure 1. BRIDGE standards [6]

Based on these considerations, this blueprint outlines the development and piloting of a mentoring programme for global health epidemiologists based on the BRIDGE guidelines. The initiative is intended as a long-term non-funded programme which leverages on professional intrinsic motivation to contribute to the committees and activities. Funding may be sought for pre-

¹ The term “reverse mentoring” can be considered misleading as it suggests something is being undone, e.g. skills unlearned. In fact the “reverse” label only refers to who is in the traditional mentor role (typically older, more senior) versus who is in the learner role (typically younger, more junior). One could argue that focusing on this role reversal reinforces outdated ideas about where knowledge should flow from. Other preferred terms might include: reciprocal mentoring, cross-generational mentoring, bidirectional mentoring. These alternatives put more emphasis on the exchange of knowledge, rather than the direction it “should” go. The point is: everyone has something valuable to teach—age or seniority does not define who gets to mentor.

specified activities (e.g. meetings or other network opportunities). This programme description is intended as a source document and describes the mentorship programme in detail, including all anticipated procedures and roles and responsibilities of different individuals and committees.

1.2 Aims and objectives

The aim of the BRIDGE mentorship initiative is to promote research integrity and fairness in global health epidemiological studies. The specific objectives are:

- 1) To equip epidemiologists with skills to become mentors on research integrity and fairness in their own networks
- 2) To offer mentorship opportunities to researchers embarking on an epidemiological study
- 3) To create a support networks of researchers committed to research fairness and integrity and to promote exchanges of best practices to deal with dilemmas related to research integrity and fairness in global health epidemiology
- 4) To create platforms to promote life-long learning and constructive dialogue as a means to create working cultures conducive for research integrity and fairness

1.3 Theory of change

We envisage the BRIDGE mentorship initiative as a transformative programme that creates significant and lasting positive changes – however small – in individuals’ research practices. Figure 2 below visualises our theory of change. While the initiative is based on the BRIDGE guidelines, we do not want to promote a superficial “tick box checking” approach. Indeed, the BRIDGE approach is meant to be dynamic and flexible: it also helps researchers find other, more specific guidance and tools. As such, BRIDGE standards and criteria are meant to provide structure to the mentoring process and act as conversation starters to guide dialogues between mentor and mentee. Through these dialogues, our aim is to bring about shifts in attitudes, behaviours and actions of mentors and mentees, with a hope that this can subsequently affect broader research environments in which they operate.

The BRIDGE mentorship initiative consists of mentoring rounds. For each round, a small group of mentors and mentees will be recruited and paired. They will follow a short online preparatory training on the essentials of research integrity, BRIDGE guidelines, and mentoring. Next, they will engage in project-based mentoring, with one-to-one exchanges between mentors and mentees based on a specific study (brought forward by the mentee) and following the steps and chronological order of the six BRIDGE standards. In addition, the programme also initiates intervision sessions to promote interaction and networking among the mentors and among the mentees. One complete mentoring round will last approximately one year. Once they have completed one round, mentors

and mentees will be invited to join a long-term BRIDGE community of practice to further enable exchanges and dialogue on research integrity and fairness matters.

With these activities, we hope that the epidemiologists who joined the programme will be equipped to recognise research integrity and research fairness dilemmas in their professional life and will be able to find resources to deal with them. While the one-to-one mentoring will represent more intense moments of exchange on a specific study, the community of practice aims to promote life-long learning, dialogue and exchanges among peers. Ultimately it is hoped that this type of approach can transform working cultures and create professional environments conducive to achieve the highest levels of scientific conduct.

Figure 1. BRIDGE mentorship initiative theory of change

1.4 BRIDGE mentoring style

The core of the BRIDGE mentorship initiative is the creation of one-on-one matches between mentors and mentees and the facilitation of structured mentee-driven exchanges (typical of coaching). As such, we will match researchers embarking on a new epidemiological study (mentees) with researchers who have either thematic or methodological expertise related to that study (mentors). Mentors may be more senior or junior than their mentees, meaning that the programme includes both traditional mentoring approaches as well as “reverse” mentoring [5]. What distinguishes mentees from their mentors is that the mentees should be involved in one concrete epidemiological research project at the time of the mentoring. The mentors, on the other hand, should have no vested interests and no management role in the research project of their mentee. Throughout the one-to-one mentoring process, the mentor and mentee meet at regular times points

to check in on progress along the lines of the BRIDGE criteria and to discuss any challenges, dilemmas, and potential solutions. The BRIDGE mentoring process is meant to be mentee-driven. This means that mentees are expected to take the lead by being proactive and taking responsibility for their learning. Mentors play a supportive role, not by prescribing actions, but by asking insightful questions to promote reflection, awareness and self-directed learning. In this sense, the BRIDGE mentoring style has many characteristics typically associated with coaching.

2. Implementation

2.1 Overall approach of the mentorship initiative

We envisage the initiative to be implemented as a series of mentoring rounds organised by different organising committees with overall guidance and oversight of the BRIDGE steering committee (Figure 3). The entire initiative is organised as a series of mentoring rounds with a duration of approximately one year each, where approximately 10 mentor/mentee pairs are created and followed up per round. Preparatory training and exchanges between mentees and mentors will be facilitated by means of a (preferably open-source) learning management system or e-learning platform.

The first round consists of the pilot round (see [Section 3](#)) during which the procedures and e-learning environment will be developed and tested. The first round will be implemented by the KIT and ITM teams that have designed the initiative. After this first round, organisations will be invited to place a bid to host a round. Organising committees for following rounds will be selected by the steering committee.

After mentors and mentees have completed a one-year mentoring round, they will be invited to join the BRIDGE community of practice (CoP). This is envisaged as an online platform that brings together all those that have been involved in the BRIDGE mentorship initiative and enables collaborative learning and knowledge sharing. **Some key functions of the BRIDGE CoP include:** **1) Knowledge sharing:** one of the primary purposes of the BRIDGE CoP is to facilitate the continuous exchange of knowledge and best practices related to research integrity and fairness among its members. Members will be able to share experiences, insights, resources and lessons learned; **2) Peer support:** the BRIDGE CoP will provide a platform for members to discuss challenging issues with regards to research integrity and fairness. Members will be able to ask questions, seek guidance, and share experiences, benefiting from the collective expertise and diverse perspectives in global health epidemiology; **3) Networking and relationship building:** the BRIDGE CoP will allow members to

connect with like-minded individuals who share their interest and passion for specific sub-fields of global health epidemiology and expand their professional networks; **4) Reflection and critical thinking:** the BRIDGE CoP will encourage members to engage in reflection and critical thinking about good epidemiological practice. Through online forum discussions, members will be encouraged to explore different viewpoints and gain new perspectives, challenge assumptions, and develop a deeper understanding of knowledge creation in global health epidemiology.

Figure 2. BRIDGE mentoring overall approach

2.2 Organisation of mentoring rounds

Each mentoring round will consist of seven phases of implementation. The organising committee that has been selected to implement the round will be responsible to implement all phases, with support and input from a member of the steering committee. An overview of the seven phases is presented below, with further details in [Table 1](#):

- 1. Recruitment and selection of mentors and mentees** (duration: 1 month): Mentees will be able to apply for the mentoring round through a call, while mentors will be selected from the existing BRIDGE network.

2. **Preparatory training for mentors and mentees** (1 month): Once a pool of mentees and mentors have identified, they will be offered self-paced training on research integrity, the BRIDGE guidelines, and mentoring, via the online e-learning platform.
3. **Project-based mentoring: application of BRIDGE guidelines** (10 months): Mentees will be matched to a mentor based on affinity with the thematic area and/or methods used in the project. Over the course of approximately 10 months, the mentee will meet their mentor eight times (once for every BRIDGE standard, plus one introductory and one wrap-up meeting), either online or in person, using the BRIDGE guidelines as a reference framework to guide discussions. The mentee will be responsible for setting up meetings with the mentor and documenting all conversations and decisions taken for each BRIDGE criterion based on discussions with the mentor.
4. **Creation of intervision² groups** (10 months, overlapping with project-based mentoring): In order to maximise opportunities for cross-learning between projects for both mentors and mentees, mentor Intersivision groups and mentee intersivision groups will be created within each round to enable mentors and mentees to network among each other.
5. **Assessment and certification** (duration: 2 weeks): At the end of a round, the organising committee awards the BRIDGE Good Epidemiological Practice certificates. Mentors and mentees can obtain a certificate on three conditions: they finished the preparatory training, completed the project-based mentoring (evidenced by the filled out BRIDGE tables), and wrote and exchanged reflective notes.
6. **Monitoring** (duration: from recruitment up to one year after certification): Each round will be followed up with a mixture of qualitative or quantitative indicators to ensure that the round is being implemented according to plan and to assess whether expected outcomes have been achieved (if intersivision groups are still active, what resources people use etc.).

² This terminology and concept derives from a practice of medical doctors in the Netherlands, who engage in a practice called "intersivision groups" as a form of professional development and peer learning. Intersivision refers to a structured and facilitated group process in which professionals come together to reflect on their work, share experiences, and support each other in problem-solving and professional growth. Intersivision groups typically consist of a small number of medical doctors, often from different specialties or healthcare settings, who meet regularly. Intersivision groups create a safe and confidential space for doctors to reflect on their professional experiences and challenges. Participants share real-life cases or situations they have encountered in their practice and explore them collectively. The focus is on understanding the complexities, underlying dynamics, and potential improvements in these cases. Through the intersivision process, participants learn from each other's perspectives, insights, and expertise. Intersivision groups contribute to the ongoing professional development of medical doctors. This continuous learning helps doctors stay up-to-date with evolving medical practices and provides opportunities for self-improvement.

7. **Closure** (duration: 1 month): Once a round has been completed, the organising committee will be requested to compile a final report to the BRIDGE steering committee which includes all documentation, so that materials can be transferred to the next host.

The time investment for one round of mentoring is as follows for mentors and mentees:

- **Mentors: approximately 31 hours over the course of one year.** Breakdown: preparatory training on essentials of research integrity, BRIDGE guidelines, and mentoring (8 hours); eight one-hour mentoring sessions with mentee with one-hour preparation each (16 hours); review of BRIDGE tables reflecting project-based mentoring, developed by mentee (2 hours); writing reflective note on the experience of being a mentor (1 hour); participation in intervision group with other mentors (3 hours, but flexible); participation in closure meeting (1 hour); filling out evaluation (15 minutes)
- **Mentees: approximately 53 hours over the course of one year.** Breakdown: preparatory training (8 hours); eight one-hour mentoring sessions with mentor with one-hour preparation each (16 hours); developing the BRIDGE tables reflecting project-based mentoring and keeping it up to date (24 hours); writing reflective note on the experience of being a mentee (1 hour); participation in intervision group with other mentees (3 hours, but flexible); participation in closure meeting (1 hour); filling out evaluation (15 minutes)

2.3 Online platform

As part of the round 1 pilot, we will develop a Moodle platform for the BRIDGE mentorship initiative, as a central place where all training material and resources will be made available and exchanges between mentors and mentees will take place. We also intend to use the Moodle platform to create a collaborative training community – the BRIDGE community of practice (CoP) – where all members will have free access to the materials created on the platform. Moodle is a free and open-source learning management system for hosting training materials and communication. As such, it is ideally suited to enable handovers from one organising committee to another. Institutions that are next in line as organising committees (after the pilot round 1 described in [Section 3](#)) can copy and modify the existing courses on Moodle or use another learning management system of their choice to run the next rounds of the mentoring programme.

Table 1. Overview of main features of a BRIDGE mentoring round

Phase	Mentors	Mentees
1. Selection of mentors and mentees	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5+ years' experience and currently actively involved in conducting or appraising global health epidemiological studies Completed postgraduate course in epidemiology Commitment towards research integrity and fairness 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> About to embark on a global health epidemiological study with approximate duration of one year Completed postgraduate course in epidemiology or related Commitment towards research integrity and fairness
2. Preparatory training	Compulsory self-paced online training covering the essentials of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Research integrity BRIDGE standards and criteria Mentoring 	
3. Project-based mentoring	Over the course of approximately ten months, the mentee will meet their mentor eight times (once for every BRIDGE standard, plus one introductory and one wrap-up meeting)	
4. Networking through intervision	Creation of intervision groups to bring mentors together	Creation of intervision groups to bring mentees together
5. Assessment and certification	Organising committee awards BRIDGE Good Epidemiological Practice certificate to mentor if: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Mentor finished preparatory training Online BRIDGE tables are complete and reflect project-based mentoring Mentor wrote reflective note on what they learned from the experience of being a mentor (approximately 200 words) and shared it with their mentee 	Organising committee awards BRIDGE Good Epidemiological Practice certificate to mentee if: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Mentee finished preparatory training Online BRIDGE tables are complete and reflect project-based mentoring Mentee wrote reflective note on what they learned from the experience of being a mentee (approximately 200 words) and shared it with their mentor
6. Monitoring	Progress reports to ensure the round is going according to plan, collection of indicators after one year relating to expected outcomes (if intervision groups are still active, what resources people use etc.).	
7. Closure	Final report to the BRIDGE steering committee and transfer of materials to the next organising committee.	

2.4 Governance

The BRIDGE mentorship initiative is held together and implemented thanks to two committees: the steering committee and the organising committee, each with their own responsibilities and decision-making authority. The steering committee consists of key experts who provide strategic direction and oversight for the mentorship initiative. Their primary role is to set the initiative's goals, establish procedures, and ensure continuity of the mentoring rounds, which includes selecting each round's organising committee. Two individuals of the steering committee will be nominated as chair and co-chair of the steering committee and will take decisions on behalf of the steering committee. The organising committee focuses on the day-to-day operations of the implementation of the mentoring round. They will handle the logistical aspects of running mentoring rounds (selecting and pairing mentors and mentees, managing the online platform, initiating intervision groups, awarding certificates, implementing monitoring activities). [Table 2](#) below provides more details about the responsibilities of each committee.

Table 2. Characteristics of steering and organising committee

Committee	Characteristics
Steering committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Primary objective: set the initiative's goals, establish procedures, and ensure continuity across mentoring rounds, which includes selecting each round's organising committee. ○ Number of members: up to eight members, for a four-year term with a maximum of two terms ○ Represented by: two chairs who take decisions on behalf of the committee. The chairs will normally work on consensus but votes can be requested and outcomes recorded in minutes ○ Responsibilities: evaluate bids and select organisations to host mentoring rounds; ensure that host organisations have comprehensively covered costs and have demonstrated interest in research integrity and fairness and represent values consistent with BRIDGE values; review any sponsors proposed for each round and refuse inappropriate ones
Organising committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Primary objective: day-to-day operations of the implementation of the mentoring round. ○ Number of members: two to three members, for a one-year term ○ Represented by: a chair (and possibly a co-chair) ○ Responsibilities: select and pair mentors and mentees, manage the online platform, initiate intervision groups, award certificates, implement monitoring activities

3. Round 1 pilot

3.1 Funding

The [datahub](#) at the Institute of Tropical Medicine in Antwerp is hosting the round 1 pilot phase of the BRIDGE mentorship initiative, which includes the development of a first version of procedures and online platform. The funding for the ITM datahub comes from the Department of Economy, Science & Innovation of the Flemish Government in Belgium. However, eventually, the initiative is intended as a long-term non-funded programme which leverages on professional intrinsic motivation to contribute to the committees and activities. Funding may be sought for pre-specified activities (e.g. meetings or other network opportunities).

3.2 Project team

The project team involved in the conception and development to the BRIDGE mentorship initiative as part of the round 1 pilot consists of two staff of the Institute of Tropical Medicine (ITM) in Antwerp, Belgium (Tine Verdonck and Lai Jiang) and two staff of KIT Royal Tropical Institute in Amsterdam, Netherlands (Sandra Alba and Mahdi Abdelwahab).

Tine Verdonck (MD, MSc, PhD) is a Belgian public health epidemiologist and statistician. She has worked from 2000 to 2011 at the Instituto de Medicina Tropical Alexander von Humboldt, Universidad Peruana Cayetano Heredia in Lima, Peru and since 2011 at ITM in Antwerp, Belgium. She obtained a PhD in Medical Sciences (University of Antwerp, 2008) with a thesis about epidemiology and clinical aspects of human T-lymphotropic virus 1 (HTLV-1) infection in Peru and an MSc in statistics (Hasselt University, 2020) with a thesis about estimating the frequency of infectious diseases in heterogeneous populations. Since 2016, she has been one of two course directors of the Master of Public Health at ITM. In terms of research interests, she is moving from general epidemiology (accuracy of diagnostic tests, role of diagnostic tests in the control of infectious diseases, quantitative evidence synthesis) to ecoepidemiology and ecohealth.

Lai Jiang (MSc, PhD) studied Educational Science and has a PhD in the field of instructional design at KULeuven in Belgium. Between 2010-2017 she coordinated an international education network, delivering professional development training in 13 countries for lecturers from the field of tropical medicine and public health. Driven by her research interests in self-regulated learning and developing higher-level thinking abilities, she contributed to an Erasmus+ project as a postdoc and lecturer at KULeuven University (2017-2019). In this collaborative effort with 11 European universities, she aimed to nurture a growth mindset among students. Lai's passion lies in understanding what makes some students effective learners while others struggle, and she explores

ways to enhance learning ability. During her time at KULeuven's central education office (2019-2021), she provided pedagogical support to all departments. Currently, as a "Teaching & Learning Expert" at ITM, she supports lecturers to create optimal learning experiences.

Sandra Alba (MSc, PhD) is an epidemiologist with a background in medical statistics. She has over 15 years' experience in the application of statistical and epidemiological methods to evaluate global health programmes. She obtained an MSc in Medical Statistics at the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine in 2006, and soon after joined the Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute to evaluate a programme aimed at improving access to malaria treatment in rural Tanzania. After completing her PhD in 2010, she spent two years working as a clinical trial statistician in Switzerland. At the end of 2012, she joined KIT as an epidemiologist. She has ample experience in designing studies, developing data collection tools, coordinating fieldwork and data management, analysing data, reporting on study results, and formulating public policy recommendations. At KIT, Sandra spearheaded the development of the BRIDGE guidelines.

Mahdi Abdelwahab (MSc, MBBCh) is a global health advisor with expertise in health education, sexual and reproductive health and rights, migrant and refugee health, and qualitative research methods. He is committed to innovation in health education, including e-learning, interactive and adaptive learning, and serious games. He has coordinated the Master of Public Health at KIT and is currently involved in several research projects. After graduating from medical school in Egypt, Mahdi moved from clinical practice to public and global health. He approaches strengthening health systems, health promotion, and working on stronger disease prevention and control as the dam that can stop the flood higher upstream rather than waiting to deal with its consequences in the valley. His experience with different organisations and entrepreneurial spirit allows him to find creative connections and opportunities for solutions and collaboration.

3.3 Timelines

Activities	2023		2024				2025				2026	
	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2
Phase 0. Blueprint and Moodle	X	X	X	X	X	X	X					
Phase 1. Selection mentors & mentees								X				
Phase 2. Preparatory training								X				
Phase 3. Project-based mentoring									X	X	X	X
Phase 4. Intervision									X	X	X	X
Phase 5. Assessment & certification												X
Phase 6. Monitoring								X	X	X	X	X
Phase 7. Closure												X

4. Annexes

Annex 1: BRIDGE Mentorship Initiative – Expression of interest letter round 1 – updated

Annex 2: BRIDGE Mentorship Initiative – Bid form for mentoring round 1 – updated

5. References

1. Horn L, Alba S, Gopalakrishna G, Kleinert S, Kombe F, Lavery JV, Visagie RG. The Cape Town Statement on fairness, equity and diversity in research. *Nature* 2023; 615(7954): 790-793.
2. Mejlgaard N, Bouter LM, Gaskell G, Kavouras P, Allum N, Bendtsen AK, Charitidis CA, Claesen N, Dierickx K, Domaradzka A, Reyes Elizondo A, Foeger N, Hiney M, Kaltenbrunner W, Labib K, Marušić A, Sørensen MP, Ravn T, Ščepanović R, Tjeldink JK, Veltri GA. Research integrity: nine ways to move from talk to walk. *Nature* 2020; 586(7829): 358-360.
3. Wocial LD. The role of mentors in promoting integrity and preventing scientific misconduct in nursing research. *J Prof Nurs* 1995; 11(5): 276-80.
4. Bird SJ. Mentors, advisors and supervisors: Their role in teaching responsible research conduct. *Sci Eng Ethics* 2001; 7: 455–468.
5. Pizzolato D, Dierickx K. Reverse mentoring to enhance research integrity climate. *BMC Res Notes* 2022; 15: 209.
6. Alba S, Verdonck K, Lenglet A, Rumisha SF, Wienia M, Teunissen I, Straetemans M, Mendoza W, Jeannotot D, Weibel D, Mayanja-Kizza H, Juvekar S. Bridging research integrity and global health epidemiology (BRIDGE) statement: guidelines for good epidemiological practice. *BMJ Glob Health* 2020; 5(10): e003236.